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Bioethical Literacy in Higher Education: Insights from Postgraduate Students

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Abstract: This qualitative study explores how Greek postgraduate students perceive bioethical literacy and its infusion within higher education curricula. Through in-depth interviews, participants emphasized bioethical literacy as a crucial tool for critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and the recognition of moral dilemmas in both academic and real-world contexts. The findings reveal a general acknowledgment of the core of bioethical literacy. Participants advocated for the systematic infusion of bioethical literacy into university curricula across disciplines, emphasizing the need for a multidisciplinary and applied approach. This research stresses bioethical literacy as an essential component for fostering ethically aware professionals capable of navigating the complexities of contemporary era.

Keywords: university students, bioethical literacy, bioethics, university curricula, ethical reflection.

Introduction

Every active member of society is, on numerous occasions throughout their social life, called upon to make decisions concerning the discernment between right and wrong, the attainment of an optimal balance between benefit and harm, the autonomous formation of moral judgment, the consideration of justice as a fundamental parameter, and the imperative to avoid causing harm. These elements constitute the moral reflection of the individual as a person, characterized by universality, autonomy, and rationality, which governs every human decision and consequent action (Mantzaridis, 2015). The ethical decisions and actions of individuals shape their behaviors, which in turn reverberate throughout society and the public sphere- a domain open to free access and expression for all, irrespective of nationality, religion, gender, age, or social class. The human being is integrated into society as an organic component of the human biosphere through a dual dynamic process: (a) by learning the conditions under which they evolve from a biological entity into a social subject, and (b) by participating in processes of teaching and learning, they chart the pathways through which, as a member of the collective, they will both preserve and transform their society through continuous social interaction and action (Tsironis, 2012). In this manner, the individual actively contributes to the shaping of social reality, both influencing and being influenced, defining and being defined.

It would not be an exaggeration to assert that, in recent decades, bioethics has claimed the "lion's share" of both academic and public discourse. It has been argued that bioethics rescued moral philosophy from excessive theoretical abstraction by providing it with a new field of engagement, one replete with challenges but also rich in interest (Toulmin, 1982). Bioethics initially emerged as the interdisciplinary field tasked with examining the ethical issues arising from the applications of contemporary biomedical technology (Koios, 2003). Although seeds of bioethical reflection can be traced back to antiquity, the widely accepted historical context for the rise of modern bioethical discourse is situated in the post-World War II era, and more specifically, in the aftermath of the atrocities exposed during the Nuremberg Trials (Koios et al., 2006). Bioethics thus began as an effort to protect the individual from the arbitrary and unrestrained use of modern biomedical technology. Over the years, and in light of developments across all spheres of social life at the threshold of the 20th and 21st centuries, the scope of bioethics has expanded to encompass additional areas such as environmental ethics, professional ethics, human rights, artificial intelligence, and neuroethics (Korff, 1998). Its initial form, focused primarily on the applications of biomedical technology, is commonly referred to as biomedical ethics. However, the concept of bioethics has gradually broadened its field of interest, tending to encompass the entirety of the modern human biosphere, and in some respects, almost replacing classical moral philosophy (Engelhardt, 2000). The above considerations lead to the following conclusion: bioethics, both in its original "narrow" interpretation and in its expanded form, creates a novel landscape of moral inquiry for every new member of society engaged in the formation of their ethical conscience. The integration of bioethical reflection into the education of future professionals not only enhances ethical decision-making but also fosters a deeper understanding of the moral implications of their practices amidst the ethical challenges posed by the rapid social and

scientific developments of our time. The first step and principal tool in this direction is bioethical literacy (Balatsou & Theologou 2021).

But what exactly do we mean by the term literacy? It can be described as the familiarization of modern individuals with complex systems of communication and codes (Pekkolay, 2022). This familiarization equips them, first, with the necessary skills for recognition and comprehension, and subsequently, with the critical concepts relevant to various contexts within social, scientific, and cultural realities. This process can be regarded as fundamental to the individual's personal development, social advancement, and active citizenship in the modern era, spanning the entirety of their life course. Thus, the earlier conception of literacy—focused primarily on alphabetization and the understanding of written texts—is now largely considered a given, at least in the majority of the Western world. It has been succeeded by new forms of literacy, emerging from new contexts and contemporary realities. It is in this context that bioethical literacy has emerged, encompassing the understanding and application of bioethical principles such as autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice—principles that can substantially improve the educational environment and foster social responsibility among future professionals (Iancu M., 2014).

The significance of bioethical literacy in higher education lies in equipping future professionals with the skills to first recognize fundamental bioethical concepts and subsequently to comprehend and engage with them in depth. This cognitive engagement will provide them with the necessary tools to address complex ethical dilemmas in their professional lives, fostering their moral competence (Kirkov et al., 2024). It encourages a holistic approach to education, wherein ethical reflection is interwoven with academic content, thereby enriching the overall learning experience (Stepanyuk & Bak, 2024). Interdisciplinary linkages in the teaching of bioethics can facilitate a comprehensive understanding of ethical principles, enabling professionals to apply these concepts across a range of issues (Daniel et al., 2016). Based on the above, the purpose of this study is to investigate the perceptions of postgraduate students in Greece regarding bioethical literacy and its integration into higher education curricula. This research is essential because its findings address a significant gap in existing literature.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The purpose of the present study is to examine postgraduate students' perceptions of bioethical literacy and its integration into higher education curricula. Based on this aim, the study addressed the following two research questions:

1st: What are postgraduate students' perceptions of bioethical literacy?

2nd: What are postgraduate students' perceptions regarding the integration of bioethical literacy into higher education curricula?

To explore these research questions, a qualitative research design was adopted, employing semi-structured online interviews, as they offer time efficiency and flexibility in scheduling (Deakin & Wakefield, 2014), with seven postgraduate students, three women and four men, enrolled in a

Department of Social Sciences and Humanities at a university in Northern Greece. Participants were selected through purposive sampling methods. It worths mentioning that even if all of them are fluent in Greek, they do not come from Greece. The interview protocol was specifically developed based on a systematic literature review. The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Recurring patterns and key points in the participants' narratives were identified and systematically categorized into themes (Creswell, 2012). Throughout the research process, ethical considerations were strictly observed, and both reliability and validity standards were upheld.

Research Results

Three themes emerged from the data collection process, shaping the framework of this study's findings. The first theme concerns how participants conceptualize bioethical literacy; the second addresses its relevance and significance in the modern era; and the third focuses on the integration of bioethical literacy into contemporary higher education curricula. From the research data it becomes evident that survey participants perceive bioethical literacy as a fundamental tool for recognizing bioethics (Int.2, Int.3). They refer to it as essential knowledge that empowers individuals to identify, process, critically analyze ethical dilemmas and evaluate possible solutions based on the bioethical principles (Int., Int.6). Also, the interviewees make the distinction between bioethical literacy and bioethics itself (Int., Int.6). However, a participant noted that, despite belonging to a scientific field closely related to bioethics, it was only through this research that came up with the concept of bioethical literacy (Int.4). Furthermore, the survey participants highlight the pivotal role of bioethical literacy both for the academic and scientific community and for broader societal development (Int.5, Int.6, Int.7). Moreover, according to their responses, bioethical literacy should be integrated into university curricula, (Int.2, Int.4, Int.5 Int.6), by an interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary approach especially in the modern era which is increasingly complex and technologically driven.

To substantiate the above, selected interview excerpts are presented below:

Int.1: "... bioethical literacy is the recognition of what constitutes justice, injustice, harm, and benefit."

Int.2: "... yes, bioethical literacy is the tool for recognizing bioethics, whereas bioethics itself is the process of inquiry, critical thinking, reflection, and ethical contemplation."

Int.3: "... bioethical literacy is the means or tool through which we recognize the term bioethics—what bioethics is, what its stages are, what its key concepts are, and what constitutes bioethics so that one can properly identify it."

Int.4: "... even though we belong to a field related to bioethics, we realize that bioethical literacy is a tool within our studies but today is actually the first time we encountered the concept, when we were asked about it as part of this research."

Int.5: "... it is about critical thinking and moral reasoning—the ability to recognize ethical dilemmas and to analyze different perspectives, to evaluate arguments on a given issue based on the principles of bioethics when facing an ethical matter."

Int.6: "... bioethical literacy is knowledge, both theoretical and practical, whereas bioethics is its application in real life."

Int.7: "... the importance of bioethical literacy in the modern era is significant because it allows one to understand core concepts across various disciplines, such as medicine, biology, philosophy, law, and sociology."

Int.6: "... it is highly important, as it enables one to recognize and manage the ethical dilemmas that arise daily around us."

Int.3: "... it is a key factor in applying the basic principles of bioethics in practice... facilitating the familiarization of both the public and specialists with the fundamental principles of bioethics, such as respect for autonomy, non-maleficence, beneficence, and justice."

Int.1: "... it is very helpful in enabling someone to work with the core principles of bioethics—autonomy, justice, beneficence, and non-maleficence."

Int.6: "... it is particularly important, as it can contribute to addressing social and bioethical issues."

Int.2: "... it should be a mandatory course in all university departments."

Int.6: "... it must be a core subject across all departments but also approached through collaboration with other disciplines. For example, in a theology school, we approach bioethics and bioethical literacy from the perspective of a theologian, someone with a particular way of thinking based on their training and expertise. But if we bring in someone from the medical field, or another department who has worked on bioethical matters, we will be exposed to another dimension that may not have been as developed or presented in our own discipline."

Int.5: "... it should be part of every university curriculum, and the approach should be multifaceted and interdisciplinary. The way it is taught at the university should involve seminars and guest lectures from experts across different fields."

Int.4: "... it should be taught in all departments, but especially in the humanities, medical sciences, and in fields related to technology."

Conclusions

This qualitative study explored Greek postgraduate students' perspectives on bioethical literacy and its incorporation into higher education curricula. The findings pointed out that postgraduate students are aware that bioethical literacy goes beyond theoretical knowledge (Balatsou & Theologou 2021), and it is an essential educational means that can cultivate ethical awareness, foster critical reflection, promote a culture of responsibility and guide not only professionals but individuals to make beneficial decisions when they are into ethical dilemmas. This result comes in agreement with Nunes et al. (2015), Maurya (2024), Kirkov et al. (2024) and Pontigo & Villegas-Delgadillo (2020). Also, the results shed light that bioethical literacy should be a core component within university curricula through multifaceted and interdisciplinary approaches, especially, in the current era that is characterized by technological advancements, biomedical innovations, and broader societal transformations. These findings are consistent with Saxena (2019) and Daniel et al. (2016).

While this study offers insights into postgraduate students' perceptions of bioethical literacy within the context of Greek higher education, there are some limitations that should be acknowledged. Firstly, it is a limited research study. Secondly, the survey participants were postgraduate students who were aware of the subject of bioethics, so their answers might have been positively biased toward the topic in question. So, future research should examine these limitations by including students from a diverse range of disciplines and exploring the development and assessment of bioethical literacy curricula as well as the long-term impact of them on the professional and personal life of university students.

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